

FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA

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TAMARAKHANIM IS A SELFLESS EXPONENT OF DANCE ART

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Abstract: This article contains information about a drama artist, a talented dancer and singer, a selfless exponent of dance art – Tamarakhonim, who is important in the development of Uzbek art for his fruitful creative work.

Keywords: Tamarakhanim, dance, uzbek folk dances, art, performance.

We confess a lot about the invaluable and unparalleled qualities of dance art. In fact, a person who realizes the inexhaustible mysterious world of dance, elegant and polished movements, the special feelings embodied in each dance, will witness how inimitable a kind of art he is. The example of creativity, which entered the world of art precisely under the name “dance”, went through a long historical period and is developing day by day. Uzbek folk dances are a huge treasure, which has captivated all art lovers. Uzbek folk dance art is as ancient and colorful as the history of our people. This art, emerging from the lifeblood of our people, has always been in development, like a living being. Each dance is passed from teachers to disciples and is coming to a new generation. One such teacher is a man of special importance in the development of Uzbek dance art with his unparalleled hard work, the “first swallow of the East” - Tamarakhanim.

Tamarakhanim's full name was Tamara Artyomovna Petrosyan, who was born in 1906 in the town of New Marghilon, Fergana region. From early childhood, a special interest and passion for the arts was instrumental in making her a singer, dancer, ballet master.

In one of his interpretative cases about him, he writes: - "I realized that my love of National Music and dance was not a "disease" to be treated, but a worthy sense of love for folk work that brought me up."

He started his first creative stage career in Hamza Hakimzoda Niyazi's troupe. And in 1920, the only female artist active in the ensemble founded by Muhiddin Koriyokubov was also exactly – the art devotee Tamarakhonim. Along with his work in the ensemble, he learned from his teachers – Muhiddin Qoriyokubov, master scientist Komilov, Yusufjon Muhar Shakarjonov, Tokhasin Jalilov, Zhurakhan

Sultanov, Khojisiddiq Islamov. The knowledge and skills that tamarakhanim acquired over the years also gave him a productive career as a dancer, singer and drama artist in musical drama productions. As he performed every image, he tried to show his love, enthusiasm and all his talent for art, and therefore, as early as 1924, he was given a beautiful definition of “the first swallow of the East”. It will not be exaggerated to say that both songs and dances in the performance of tamarakhanim have a worthy place in the hearts of our art-loving people. She is the first Uzbek creative woman to adapt Uzbek folk lapar and yallas to the stage setting. Of the lapars played by Tamarakhanim in particular – “The Eagle”, “The Bear”, “The Orphan's procession”, “the Children of Erk”, “Lolahan”, “The bracelet”, “From the path of the factory”, “Gulyor”, “The stable” - are examples of invaluable creativity. He also made a special contribution to the development of Uzbek dance art with his baletmeister skills. Staged-such dances as “Dilkhijro”, “Usmaniya”, “Sinahiroj”, “Qarinavo” took a worthy place from the hearts of art lovers. In addition, Margilan “Yallama yorim”, Kokand “with the early”, Andijan “Omonyor”, “Fargana dance”, “Bukhara dance”, “Mavrigi”, Khorezm “Lazgi”, Turkmen “Bibijon”, Georgian “wedding wedding”, Mongolian “New Moon”, Ozorbayjan “door hook”, Azeri “Chando”, Turkish “Gulizor”, Arabic “Humor”, “Binti Indonesia shalobia”, Korean “Torazi”, “Shepherd's dance”, Japanese “Mount Banday”, Hindi “Nilufar”, Afghan “Sweet zabor”, Kyrgyz “Parizaday”, Tajik “Lady of Johra, a total of more than 500 songs and dances, such as the Tatar “Garmonchi”, were performed by Tamarakhanim in 86 languages.

As noted above, Tamarakhanim was a versatile talent. Not only did he use the Persian style of dance, but also deservedly mastered the songs and dances of the oasis of Khwarezm, which made its name for its glorious history and charm, and as a result, at the 1935 London dance and music festival, together with his mentor master scientist Komilov, they demonstrated Uzbek art to the world and were awarded gold medals. And in 1937, he was also a worthy participant in the first Uzbek art deced in Moscow, and made another invaluable contribution to the development of Uzbek dance art.

Together with his mentor master scientist Komilov, he brought to the attention of the audience the “circle lesson”, which is important in the development of the Uzbek professional dance school, and the ballet works “Navo”, “spring”, “war of red and white roses”, in which the movements of European classical ballet dances are combined with Uzbek folk dances. Such performances were instrumental in the rise of the National Uzbek ballet as well as in the development of choreographic art. In 1938, the Tamarakhanim composer E.Brusilovsky's ballet” Gulandom " is harmoniously set to a libretto by and. Together with the yanovskys, he performed the stage and the lead role.

During his creative career, tamarakhanim went on a creative journey in many cities of the world and glorified Uzbek art all over the world.

The street on which he settled in Tashkent is named after Tamarakhanim. Today, the Tamarakhanim House Museum operates in the Mirzo Ulugbek District of Tashkent. Taking place from Mezei-dresses, various commemorative badges and awards, historical photographs, documents, reviews published in newspapers and magazines, you will once again witness how great the master has a place in Uzbek art.

Such effective creative activity of mentors has always been an example for us young people and can literally motivate us to become a professional cadre in our chosen profession!

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